

multidentate ligand having two pairs of chelates in the same ring of the molecule.

The Job's method of continuous variation fails to indicate a definite account of the complexation as the graph shows sufficient rounding at the peak. This seems to support our contention, of course indirectly, that either a weak complex or more than one complexes are being formed. As such the Job's method cannot be employed for any decisive information regarding the metal ligand ratio in the complex.

The spectrophotometric study by mole ratio method and the subsequent calculation of stability constants reveal the following important observations :

(i) The stepwise complexation of the metal and ligand takes place in the ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 which may be represented as ML^{+2} , ML_2^+ and ML_3 respectively.

(ii) The 1 : 1 complex is very much unstable in comparison to the other two complexes formed.

(iii) The stability constant and the corresponding free energy decrease of ML_3 (1 : 3 complex) are much greater than those of ML_2^+ (1 : 2).

On the basis of above conclusions it appears that stability increases with decrease of charge on the metal ion due to chelation and consequent desolvation of the species formed. Thus the stability constant of 1 : 3 complex (ML_3) being maximum appears to be quite reasonable.

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The Kinetics and Mechanism of Alkaline Hydrolysis of *o*-Methoxybenzamide

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THE kinetics of the hydrolysis of *o*-methoxybenzamide was studied under strongly alkaline medium. The observed pseudo first order rate constants were found to follow the empirical relationship

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = B_1 + \frac{B_2}{[\text{OH}^-]}$$

The linear parameters B_1 and B_2 were evaluated using linear least square technique. On the basis of the observed results a plausible mechanism was proposed. The temperature dependence of hydrolysis was also studied and various activation parameters were evaluated.

The kinetics of hydrolysis of *o*-methoxybenzamide was studied by Ried¹ who postulated a second order reaction in dilute acid and base solutions. Bruce and Tanner², while studying the effect of neighbouring hydroxyl groups in amide hydrolysis, gave the pH-rate profile of *o*-methoxybenzamide in very low alkaline range. No work on the hydrolysis of amides in highly alkaline medium has been reported and, therefore, in continuation of our work^{3,4} on this problem under these conditions, it was thought worthwhile to study the hydrolysis of *o*-methoxybenzamide.

Experimental

Materials : *o*-Methoxybenzamide (Aldrich) was used as such without further purification. Its freshly prepared solution in 10% ethanol was used for each set. All the other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade. Nessler's reagent was prepared by the method as described by Vogel⁵.

Kinetic Measurements :

A two-necked flask fitted with a double walled condenser, in order to check any kind of evaporation, was thermostated in an oil bath at the desired temperature. The requisite volumes of all the solutions except sodium hydroxide were taken in the flask. The reaction was started by adding the known volumes of sodium hydroxide solution and zero time was taken when half sodium hydroxide solution was transferred into the flask. As the reaction proceeded, the evolved ammonia was swept out by a continuous current of nitrogen and was absorbed in 0.05 M hydrochloric acid^{6,7} at different time intervals. The absorbed ammonia was then estimated spectrophotometrically by Nesslerization. The spectrophotometric measurements were made on a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20.

Results

The temperature dependence of hydrolysis of *o*-methoxybenzamide was studied at four different temperatures. The various activation parameters were evaluated using the Arrhenius and Eyring^{1,4} equations by linear least square technique. The values are $\Delta F^{\ddagger}85^{\circ} = 27.29$ K cal/mole; $E_a = 10.81 \pm 0.18$ K cal/mole; $\Delta H^{\ddagger} = 10.12 \pm 0.19$ K cal/mole; $\Delta S^{\ddagger} = -49.90 \pm 0.54$ e.u. and $\ln A = 6.52 \pm 0.53$ sec⁻¹.

Sodium hydroxide concentration dependence of hydrolysis was studied within its concentration range of 0.5 *M* to 2.8 *M* at 85°. The ionic strength was kept constant at 3.0 *M* by sodium nitrate solution. The observed pseudo first order rate constants were found best fit to the empirical equation (1)

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = B_1 + \frac{B_2}{[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (1)$$

Here B_1 and B_2 are arbitrary constants including some equilibrium and velocity constants. The values of B_1 and B_2 were evaluated using linear least square technique and are $(2.71 \pm 0.10) \times 10^8$ *M* sec and $(7.29 \pm 0.10) \times 10^9$ *M* sec respectively.

The effect of ionic strength was studied at 85° within the range of 2.0 to 3.2 *M*, maintained by sodium nitrate. The observed results were found independent of ionic strength.

Discussion

Bender *et al*^{1,5,16} proposed the formation of monoanionic tetrahedral intermediate by the study of oxygen isotope exchange and hydrolytic reaction of amides. Later on, Biechler and Taft¹⁷ proposed similar intermediates in the hydrolysis of trifluoroacetanilide and put forward a relation between K_{obs} and $[\text{OH}^-]$. Equation (1), derived on the basis of our measurements, is similar to that described by Biechler and Taft.¹⁷ The probable mechanism consistent with the observed results is shown in Scheme 1.

The steady state treatment to the reactive tetrahedral addition intermediate (I) gives the rate equation (2)

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{OH}^-]}{\left(1 + \frac{K_a}{K_w} [\text{OH}^-]\right) (k_{-1} + k_2)} \quad \dots (2)$$

Equation (2) is reduced to equation (3) if $k_{-1} \gg k_2$ which implies that there exists a rapid equilibrium between *o*-methoxybenzamide and tetrahedral intermediate

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{OH}^-]}{1 + \frac{K_a}{K_w} [\text{OH}^-]}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{K_a}{K_w K_1 k_2} + \frac{1}{K_1 k_2 [\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{where } K_1 = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}}$$

Scheme 1

Equation (3) is similar to the best fitted empirical equation (1) with $B_1 = \frac{K_a}{K_w K_1 k_2}$ and $B_2 = \frac{1}{K_1 k_2}$. The ratio B_1/B_2 gives the value of K_a/K_w which is ≈ 0.37 at 85°. The acidity constant of amide proton of salicylamide⁸ $\left(\frac{K_{a2}}{K_w} = 0.099$ at 95°) was found a little less than that of *o*-methoxybenzamide which is acceptable because the ionized hydroxyl group in salicylamide reduces the acidity of amide group.

Although Scheme 1 is sufficient to account for the rate data where the conjugate base \bar{A} is taken as unreactive species¹⁷ yet an alternative reaction path assuming \bar{A}^- as a reactive species^{18,19} cannot be excluded.

Here the intermediate II is the same as I in Scheme 1 and the kinetic equation derived including this additional step will have the same dependence on hydroxide ion concentration as shown by equations (2) and (3).

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Azine Dyes as Redox Indicators in Dichrometry*

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THE use of azine dyes as redox indicators in dichrometry has not been reported till now. In continuation of our recent studies on the use of some azine dyes as cerimetric redox indicators¹, we have examined the suitability of six azine dyes, Phenosafranine (PS), Methylene Violet (MV), Amethyst Violet (AV), Safranin T (ST), Wool Fast Blue BL (WFBBL) (Colour Index Nos. 50200, 50210, 50225, 50240 and 50315 respectively) and Aposafraanine (AS), having the following structures, as indicators in the dichrometric titrations of iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II), arsenic(III), uranium(IV), molybdenum(V) and hydroquinone in media of sulphuric,

hydrochloric, perchloric and phosphoric acids. Our studies have shown that the titrations of iron(II), uranium(IV) and molybdenum(V) are feasible in sulphuric, hydrochloric and perchloric acids but not in phosphoric acid medium, whereas titrations of hexacyanoferrate(II), arsenic(III) and hydroquinone are not possible in any acid medium.

Experimental

0.1 N solutions of iron(II), uranium(IV), and molybdenum(V) were prepared and standardised. 0.1 N solution of potassium dichromate was also prepared.

0.1% solutions of the dyes were prepared in deionised water. Wool Fast Blue BL was Bayer sample and the other five dyes were Gurr samples.

Phenosafranine : R₁=R₄=H; R₂=R₃=NH₂.
C. I. No. 50200

Methylene Violet : R₁=R₄=H; R₂=NH₂; R₃=N(CH₃)₂.
C. I. No. 50210

Amethyst Violet : R₁=R₄=H; R₂=R₃=N(C₂H₅)₂.
C. I. No. 50225

Safranin T : R₁=R₄=CH₃; R₂=R₃=NH₂.
C. I. No. 50240

Aposafraanine : R₁=R₂=R₄=H; R₃=NH₂.

Wool Fast Blue BL
C. I. No. 50315

Other chemicals used were of reagent grade quality.

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